

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KOUAME JEAN****FIRST NAME: KONAN****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Definition of the subject of the scientific text (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Characteristics and style of a scientific article (EUCLID 2021, 7-10) (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
3. Steps to writing a scientific article (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

SCIENTIFIC ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

Sir Winston Churchill in a quote said that writing is an adventure. At first, it is a game, then it is a lover, then it is a master, and then it is a tyrant.

The publication of scientific articles can meet several objectives. Whether they are more personal or more based on exchange, they are always part of the researcher's and doctoral student's "duty": that of sharing their discoveries.

A scientific essay is one of the best ways to make one's research known and to associate one's name with particular expertise. Researchers who publish regularly can then become references in certain fields and be frequently cited as references in other articles or books.

Even if they allow a name to be associated with particular expertise, articles are above all a place for exchange and co-construction. However individual it may be, the aim

of the research is always to be read and to elicit reactions: interpretations, questions, objections, validations, or further study.

Often expressed through quotations and references, these reactions take place in another article and contribute to the formation of a certain "dialogue", often international in scope.

Any researcher, whether a doctoral student, a laboratory researcher, a teacher-researcher, or an expert, does not publish only to make himself known and to exchange.

The main objective of the research is to advance the state of knowledge in many fields. To do this, sharing is necessary: conferences and the publication of articles or books are the most common means. Being a researcher, therefore, implies being a lecturer and an author (Warburton 2009).

In this response paper, I will present how to define the subject of the scientific text, the characteristics, and style of a scientific article and the steps to writing a scientific article, and the imperative to avoid plagiarism.

1) DEFINITION OF THE SUBJECT OF THE SCIENTIFIC TEXT

The problem of choosing a topic depends on two things:

To deal with a subject scientifically, it must be mastered. It is advisable to remain focused on our field of expertise; this will allow us to be more credible and to have ease of research work (EUCLID 2021, 7-14).

The problem must be original and precise. Writing a scientific article on a subject that is already too well known would be pointless. The research paper aims to bring new elements to open up new scientific avenues and debates.

The starting question must be as precise as possible, firstly to avoid wasting time in writing and secondly to arouse the curiosity of the readers (Gemayel 2016) Characteristics and style of a scientific article

2.1 Characteristics of a scientific article

As far as the characteristics of a scientific article are concerned, it must

- Have a precise topic, i.e. a single main axis with a conclusion

- Have precise language with the use of numbers, symbols and s, and equations with a scientific tone. The terminology used is very important, avoiding synonyms It must be a very focused article to draw a conclusion.
- A complete article, concise and contains all the details to understand and reproduce the results. The emphasis should be on popularisation and showing the possible benefits for society.
- The article should have a very good structure by making it clear how you are going to address the question, where you, by setting out your main ideas clearly and making it clear how the main ideas relate to each other and taking the reader through your answer in a logical, progressive way (“Comprendre et Maîtriser La Littérature Scientifique - Bernard Pochet - Google Livres” n.d.).

2.2 Style d'un article scientifique

There is a different style of a scientific article (“Comprendre et Maîtriser La Littérature Scientifique - Bernard Pochet - Google Livres” n.d.)

Academic writing style: Stella Cottrell (2003) refers to three main styles used in academic writing: descriptive, argumentative, and evaluative. Many writing tasks will involve some combination of the three and the use of critical, analytical skills. Some courses will require a degree of more personal, reflective writing. Some guidelines are provided here, but see the separate online guide on reflective writing for further guidance if this type of writing is required in your course.

Descriptive writing: consists of different purposes: (i) to describe what happened: e.g. main events. methods, findings (ii) to describe the main features or functions: e.g. of a policy, or practice (iii) to summarize the main points: e.g. of a theory or article.

Argumentative Writing by arguing a case/point of view, to influence the reader's thoughts/actions

Evaluative Writing by comparing finding points of similarity, contrasting finding points of difference, and evaluating the significance of similarities and differences.

3) STEPS TO WRITING A SCIENTIFIC ARTICLE

Writing a text for a scientific paper follows a structured protocol, it is an academic task and it is important to respect the codes (“Écrire et Publier Un Essai - Michel Dorais - Google Livres” n.d.).

Before starting to write, always keep in mind two essential elements: (i) the article must flow and be captivating, (ii) one concept equals one explanation. without this basic principle, you risk losing your readers as soon as the first more technical concepts are

mentioned (EUCLID 2021, 10) (“Writing for Publication: Structure, Form, Content, and Journal Selection - PMC” n.d.).

Step 1: the title and summary of the research article

Choosing the title of your scientific text requires some thought. it is the first thing the reader will see about the article. it should give the essential information while being short and captivating.

It is sometimes a good idea to write only the last part of the summary, as it summarises your article. it will serve to highlight the subject matter, the issues that arise, and the conclusions that are reached.

Step 2: Introduction

The introduction presents the subject by raising the issue to emphasize the importance of the research article. it allows you to demonstrate an information gap and the relevance of responding to it. to do this, your introduction should follow a few principles: (i) start by explaining the importance of your research, (ii) next, state the question that stems from it, and (iii) describe the objective or hypotheses of the article.

Step 3: Methodology

One of the principles of scientific writing is to detail the methods used in your research. you should describe the different stages of your work and your thinking clearly and concisely. the methodology should follow an experimental protocol.

We must provide all the necessary details so that the reader can reproduce your research journey: the collection of data, their analysis, and the main stages of your research. The description of your research method must allow you to validate or invalidate the initial hypothesis (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Step 4: Results

This is the most important part of your scientific text as it is the culmination of your research. It is the place to present the results and analysis objectively. The research article aims to enable the reader to reach his or her conclusions.

Whether presented in text, tables, or graphs, the results should be understandable and relevant.

Step 5: Discussion

The discussion section will allow you to present your conclusions. to make it easier to read, make one paragraph per idea and start the section with the conclusion, then demonstrate your conclusion.

This section is used to highlight your scientific work, particularly by comparing it with that of other scientists.

The discussion also includes the limitations of the research, and how you have overcome these to obtain convincing results (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Step 6: the conclusion

The conclusion of your scientific paper should repeat the questions asked, summarise the answers and reiterate the need for your research. It can also end with an open question, leading to another research topic raised by your article (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Step 7: the bibliography

A scientific article inevitably relies on the work of others. It is, therefore, necessary to cite its sources and bibliographical references.

4) PLAGIARISM

Is academic plagiarism, only an ethical issue?

The term 'academic plagiarism' is chosen here to refer to student plagiarism and plagiarism in scientific research. It also allows us to include the practices of teachers in their training. Echoing the remark of the student plagiarist quoted in the introduction, I do not wish to separate these issues (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Plagiarism has several consequences: destroying student reputation, destroying professional reputation, destroying academic reputation with legal repercussions and monetary repercussions.

The consequences of plagiarism are far-reaching, and no one is immune. Neither ignorance nor stature excuses a person from the ethical and legal ramifications of committing plagiarism. Before attempting any writing project, learn about plagiarism and why citations are established academic methods of avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34).

5) CONCLUSION

Publishing content in a scientific journal is a source of many benefits for researchers, as well as for the research community. It contributes to the expansion of research. The scientific journal is a medium that allows the dissemination of discoveries and information, the opening of a debate, or an argument. It is a means of communication that allows researchers and doctoral students from all over the world to enrich each other.

Scientific writing is the medium that a researcher uses to read. He/she thus obtains visibility and his/her text can be quoted, commented on, or criticized.

Therefore it is necessary to respect the characteristics and style, follow the different steps to writing a scientific essay meticulously, and be careful not to fall into plagiarism.

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